

Paglets: Explicit-State Mobile Agents for Python Host Meshes

Christian Klukas¹

June 23, 2026

Abstract. Mobile agents offered a direct programming model for computations that move between networked hosts, carrying behavior and state closer to the resources they need. IBM’s Java Aglets system made this idea concrete with a mobile-agent API, proxies, message passing, dispatch, retraction, activation, and deactivation. Paglets revisits the same family of ideas for modern Python, but deliberately narrows the mobility model: code is not uploaded at movement time, Python stacks and live resources do not migrate, and every mobile object carries explicit dataclass state that can be serialized, inspected, persisted, and moved between trusted hosts. This paper introduces the Paglets runtime, explains how it relates to Aglets, and outlines practical use cases for infrastructure inspection, data-local analytics, distributed examples, and stateful agent workflows. A small two-host evaluation illustrates movement latency, payload transfer speed, and host-local benchmark behavior on a mixed macOS and Windows mesh.

Keywords: mobile agents; Python; Aglets; distributed systems; dataclass state; process isolation; trusted meshes

1 Introduction

Most distributed applications are written as stationary services. A client sends requests to a server, the server performs an operation, and state usually stays behind an API boundary. This model is reliable and familiar, but it is not the only useful way to think about distributed computation. In several workflows the unit of work is naturally stateful, long-running, and location-aware: it should visit hosts, inspect local context, talk to resident services, keep progress, and return with a compact result. The mobile-agent literature explored this model in the 1990s and asked when it was better to move a computation than to move all data and control traffic through a central process [3, 8].

Paglets is a compact Python runtime in that lineage. A paglet is a mobile object with identity, explicit state, lifecycle hooks, message handling, proxy-based control, cloning, dispatch, retraction, and durable deactivation [5, 6]. It is inspired by Java Aglets, but it is not a Java Aglets clone. Paglets adapts the idea to Python’s strengths and risks: dataclasses are used as the durable state boundary; each active paglet runs in its own child Python process; movement transfers the paglet class name, state class name, identity, and serialized state; and every target host is expected to already have compatible code installed.

That choice is the central design point. Paglets does not attempt strong mobility in the sense of moving a suspended call stack, open file descriptors, sockets, arbitrary object graphs, or threads. It also does not attempt to transport executable Python code to an unprepared host. Instead, it treats mobility as explicit state relocation plus a known behavior reference. This weaker mobility model is easier to reason about, fits Python packaging, and keeps the trust model honest: Paglets is for trusted local or LAN meshes and controlled relay deployments, not for accepting untrusted executable code from the Internet.

This note makes three practical contributions. First, it documents the explicit state mobility contract used by Paglets. Second, it describes the host, child-process, mesh, persistence, and transport boundaries that make the runtime usable in Python. Third, it reports reproducible benchmark runs from a real two-machine mesh so that movement overhead and host-local performance are visible rather than only described qualitatively.

¹ORCID: 0000-0001-7956-0294

2 Background: From Aglets to Paglets

Aglets presented mobile agents as Java objects that could move between hosts, obtain access to local services, communicate by messages, and provide a uniform model that covered stationary and mobile objects [8]. The Aglets project website described Aglets as a Java platform and library for mobile-agent applications, originally developed at IBM Tokyo Research Laboratory and later hosted as an open-source SourceForge project [11]. The programming model included an Aglets platform, agent contexts, proxies, message passing, mobility operations, and lifecycle callbacks [7].

Operationally, the Aglets 2 platform exposed a standalone host called Tahiti. The user could dispatch an agent to another platform, retract a migrated agent, deactivate it into serialized local storage, and activate it again later [1]. These concepts made the agent visible as a first-class runtime object: not just a remote procedure endpoint, but an entity with location, identity, lifecycle, and state.

Paglets is also related to broader work on actors, agent interoperability, and distributed Python task systems. The actor model treats independent entities as message-processing units [4], while FIPA specifications standardized abstract services and communication concepts for interoperable agent platforms [2]. Systems such as Ray and Dask provide large-scale distributed tasks, actors, and dataflow execution for Python [9, 10]. Paglets occupies a narrower point in this space: it does not try to be a general cluster scheduler or a public mobile-code platform. Its focus is explicit state mobility, lifecycle, and message passing inside a trusted Python host mesh.

Paglets carries forward that vocabulary while changing the engineering contract. Table 1 summarizes the main differences.

Table 1. Conceptual comparison between Aglets and Paglets.

Area	Aglets	Paglets
Language and runtime	Java mobile-agent platform and API	Python package and host runtime
Mobile unit	Java aglet object hosted by an Aglets platform	Paglet identity plus explicit dataclass state and importable class reference
Code mobility	Designed around Java code and object mobility between platforms	No code upload during movement; all hosts must already import the same code
Lifecycle	Creation, dispatch, arrival, deactivation, activation, and related events	Creation, dispatch, arrival, clone, activation, deactivation, disposal, and run hooks
Communication	Proxies and messages	Proxies, typed message objects, synchronous, one-way, future-style, and multicast patterns
Isolation	Aglets execute inside the Java platform environment	Each active paglet runs in a separate child Python process
Trust model	Java-era platform security and mobile-code concerns	Explicitly trusted meshes, API-key protected HTTP, relay mode, and no untrusted-code sandbox

3 The Paglets Programming Model

A paglet author defines two things: a dataclass state object and a paglet class. The state is the durable mobile part. Ordinary Python instance attributes are treated as transient process-local data. The paglet class supplies lifecycle hooks and a message handler.

Listing 1. A minimal paglet with explicit state.

```
from dataclasses import dataclass, field

from paglets.core.agent import Paglet, PagletState
from paglets.core.messages import Message

@dataclass
class TravellerState(PagletState):
    visits: list[str] = field(default_factory=list)
    home_url: str = ""

class Traveller(Paglet[TravellerState]):
    State = TravellerState

    def on_creation(self, event):
        self.state.visits.append(f"created: {event.host_name}")

    def on_arrival(self, event):
        self.state.visits.append(f"arrived: {event.host_name}")

    def handle_message(self, message: Message):
        if message.kind == "status":
            return {"host": self.context.name, "visits": self.state.visits}
        return self.not_handled()
```

This design makes mobility visible in the source code. If a field must survive dispatch, clone, deactivation, or host restart, it belongs in the dataclass state. If a value is tied to the current process, such as a thread, socket, database handle, open file, subprocess, or cached service client, it should be created after arrival or activation and cleaned up before disposal or dispatch.

Paglets supports familiar mobile-agent operations:

- **Create** starts a paglet on a host and invokes creation lifecycle logic.
- **Dispatch** moves the current paglet to another host.
- **Clone** leaves the original paglet in place and sends a copy of its state to another host.
- **Retract** brings a moved paglet back when the caller has a valid proxy and host information.
- **Deactivate** stops the active child process and persists inactive state.
- **Activate** restores an inactive paglet from durable state.
- **Dispose** terminates the paglet and cleans associated resources.

Communication is message-oriented. A caller uses a proxy to send a `Message` to a paglet. The runtime supports direct replies, one-way delivery, future-style replies, and multicast. Inside one paglet process, normal message handling is actor-like and serial, which keeps state reasoning simpler. Parallel work is achieved by cloning or creating multiple paglet instances, not by running many concurrent message handlers inside one object.

4 Runtime Architecture

The runtime is split into a host process and child processes. The host owns identity, routing, persistence records, mesh state, admin endpoints, relay queues, and movement orchestration. Active paglet behavior runs in child Python processes started with Python’s spawn method. This design has a cost: process startup and inter-process communication are heavier than an in-memory object call. It also has useful properties: a crash in one paglet does not directly kill the host, CPU-heavy paglets can use multiple cores, and host supervision has a clear boundary around mobile state.

Figure 1. Simplified Paglets runtime architecture. The mobile part is the explicit dataclass state plus an importable class reference; active behavior runs in supervised child processes.

Remote control uses an HTTP API. Small control data is JSON. Movement uses a binary state envelope rather than forcing large mobile state through JSON. The runtime streams large payloads for host-to-host movement and uses a local handoff path when movement stays inside the same host process. The same design supports the mesh benchmark example, where a traveler paglet moves across host pairs and records directional movement timing.

Hosts can discover each other through a mesh registry. Mesh entries include version information so that a paglet is not sent to a host that probably cannot import the same classes. For networks where inbound ports are difficult, a relay mode allows outbound-only hosts to communicate through a public HTTPS endpoint. In shared networks and relay deployments, API-key authentication should be enabled. This is a practical authentication layer, not a substitute for a full mobile-code sandbox.

5 What Paglets Does Differently

The most important difference from classical Aglets is that Paglets separates mobile state from installed code. Aglets emerged in a Java setting where mobile code, object serialization, bytecode portability, and platform security were central concerns. Paglets assumes a different deployment model: code is shipped by normal software delivery mechanisms, and mobile execution means moving a known class reference plus explicit state between hosts that already trust and understand that code.

This gives Paglets a smaller but sharper contract:

1. **State is explicit.** A paglet moves with a dataclass, so authors decide what is durable and mobile.
2. **Code is importable, not uploaded.** Target hosts must have the same package or application code available by module path.

3. **Processes isolate active agents.** Each active paglet runs outside the host process, improving crash containment and CPU parallelism.
4. **Messages stay simple.** The control plane is JSON-oriented, while mobile state can use a binary envelope for Python dataclass values.
5. **Security assumptions are explicit.** Paglets is intended for trusted meshes. It does not claim to safely execute arbitrary code from unknown senders.

These differences make Paglets less ambitious than strong mobile-code systems, but more approachable for Python projects where the application owner controls the participating hosts. The model is especially natural when hosts are development machines, lab machines, edge devices, compute nodes, or servers in one administrative domain.

6 How Paglets Can Be Used

Paglets is a good fit when moving a compact stateful computation is simpler than centralizing all data access. Practical examples include:

Infrastructure inspection. A paglet can visit hosts, query local disk usage, service status, logs, package versions, or machine metadata, and return a summarized report. This avoids streaming raw logs or opening every local interface to a central service.

Data-local analytics. When data is large or sensitive, a paglet can move to the data-holding host, perform filtering or aggregation locally, and return only compact results. This pattern is useful for local search, privacy-preserving summaries, and per-site metrics.

Distributed benchmarking and examples. The project includes example agents and CLIs for system information, mesh information, Pi computation, search, performance checks, and mesh movement benchmarking. These examples exercise the actual runtime paths: paglets are created, cloned, moved, messaged, and collected rather than mocked as static function calls.

Stateful workflows. A long-running workflow can carry progress, partial results, retry state, an itinerary, and next-step logic. Instead of requiring a central orchestrator to drive every small action, the workflow object can continue from the host where it currently has useful local context.

Agent-to-agent systems. Resident service paglets can represent local expertise: disk inspection, process information, logs, instruments, databases, model adapters, or other host-bound resources. Visiting paglets communicate with those resident agents through messages and proxies. This preserves local control while still allowing mobile coordination.

AI-assisted work contexts. For LLM-backed systems, the mobile part often does not need to be the model. It can be the work context: task description, constraints, memory summary, partial findings, host itinerary, and tool permissions. A paglet can carry that context to a host that has a local model adapter or domain service, ask for analysis, and return with summarized results.

7 Evaluation

The following measurements use two hosts connected over a private 1 Gbit/s LAN: a 2022 Mac Studio with an Apple M1 Max and 32 GB RAM, and a Windows 11 Pro 25H2 workstation with an Intel Core i7-8700K CPU, 64 GB RAM, and an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 Ti. Both hosts used explicit LAN bindings on port 8765. The movement benchmark ran ten repeats for each payload

size, with seven clock probes per arrival host. The performance benchmark ran for two seconds per CPU and memory kernel and used 64 MB temporary disk files. Both hosts reported Python 3.14.6 during the performance run. These measurements are intended to characterize this Paglets runtime path on one practical mesh; they are not calibrated hardware or network benchmarks.

7.1 Movement Across Payload Sizes

The mesh movement benchmark sent one traveler paglet across every directed host pair, including self-pairs, for ten repeats. Each run measured 40 movements and reported no movement errors. Table 2 summarizes the end-to-end movement series. Average movement time stayed below 0.34 s through 16 MB payloads, rose to 0.69 s at 64 MB, and reached 8.76 s at 1 GB. At large payloads, benchmark time is dominated by end-to-end state movement rather than clock probes or route overhead.

Table 2. Mesh movement summary for the dense payload series. Times are seconds.

Payload	Moves	Avg. move	Travel	Probe round trips	Overhead	Overall
0	40	0.219	8.766	19.688	10.922	20.400
1 MB	40	0.229	9.160	20.121	10.961	20.812
4 MB	40	0.246	9.829	20.720	10.891	21.460
16 MB	40	0.334	13.377	24.327	10.950	25.083
64 MB	40	0.694	27.769	38.578	10.808	39.651
256 MB	40	2.111	84.454	101.976	17.523	104.149
512 MB	40	4.112	164.479	195.749	31.271	199.492
1 GB	40	8.763	350.519	410.063	59.544	417.017

Figure 2 shows directional movement latency by payload size. Cross-host movement is asymmetric in this run: at 1 GB, Mac-to-Windows movement averaged 16.98 s, while Windows-to-Mac averaged 12.66 s. Same-host movement was faster, but also host-dependent: Mac self-movement averaged 1.29 s at 1 GB, while Windows self-movement averaged 4.12 s. This reflects the combined runtime, host, OS, storage, and LAN conditions of this specific mesh.

Figure 2. Mean paglet movement time by payload size and direction. The zero-payload baseline is listed in Table 2; the log-scaled figure shows nonzero payload runs.

Figure 3 reports effective payload throughput derived from the same runs. Byte-throughput units use binary scaling, so MB/s means bytes per second divided by 1024^2 . Mac self-host payload movement was the fastest path in this run, peaking at 871 MB/s at 512 MB and remaining 792 MB/s at 1 GB. Windows self-host movement reached 249 MB/s at 1 GB. Cross-host effective throughput was lower and asymmetric; at 1 GB it was 81 MB/s for Windows-to-Mac and 60 MB/s for Mac-to-Windows. These rates are end-to-end Paglets movement rates, not calibrated network line-rate measurements.

Figure 3. Effective payload transfer speed by payload size. Values come from Paglets’ movement benchmark summaries, grouped by self-host and cross-host delivery relation.

7.2 Host Performance

The host performance benchmark cloned workers to both online mesh hosts and collected local CPU, memory, and disk metrics. Table 3 reports the successful single-core and multi-process CPU measurements, memory copy throughput, and the highest combined read/write disk result for each host. The “errors” column counts benchmark subtests that failed on that host. In this run, both hosts completed all reported CPU, memory, and disk subtests; no host-level errors or cleanup errors were reported.

Table 3. Host-local performance benchmark results. Byte-throughput columns use binary-scaled GB/s. CPU columns show single-core/multi-process rates.

Host	Python	CPUs	Int	Float	SHA	Mem	Disk wr/read	Meta	Errors
mac-studio	3.14.6	10	12.94 / 87.32	13.34 / 105.08	2.04 / 16.02	43.04	2.93 / 16.52	7,923	0
windows11	3.14.6	12	8.25 / 43.25	9.97 / 48.32	0.50 / 3.01	14.44	3.79 / 1.74	1,746	0

8 Software Availability and Reproducibility

Paglets is available as an MIT-licensed open-source project on GitHub [5]. User documentation is published separately [6]. The paper source, benchmark JSON files, derived tables, and plotting scripts are kept under `papers/paglets-application-note/`; the paper-specific branch is `overview-paper`, mirrored from the main repository history. The manuscript is rebuilt from the repository root with `make -C papers/paglets-application-note`, which derives TSV files from the checked-in benchmark JSON using `jq`, renders figures with `gnuplot`, and runs `latexmk`. The benchmark hosts reported Python 3.14.6, and the mesh runs used the project’s development mesh version label, `dev`.

9 Limitations and Appropriate Boundaries

Paglets should not be used as a replacement for ordinary HTTP APIs, queues, or job runners when a request/response service is simpler. It is also not a secure execution environment for unknown code. Hosts must already have compatible code installed, classes must be importable by module path, and movement does not preserve Python stacks, threads, sockets, or arbitrary live resources.

The process-per-paglet design gives useful isolation, but it means very small high-frequency work should be batched or implemented as resident service operations. Message handling is serial per paglet instance, so a parent paglet should avoid blocking inside a handler while waiting for child result messages that need the same mailbox. A better pattern is to start work, return quickly, let workers send result messages, and expose a separate status or summary message for collection.

The trust boundary should be considered part of the programming model. Paglets is appropriate for trusted local development, lab networks, controlled servers, and authenticated relay deployments. It is not designed to receive arbitrary agents from the public Internet.

10 Conclusion

Aglets demonstrated that mobile agents could be programmed as first-class distributed objects with lifecycle, identity, messaging, and movement. Paglets revisits that idea for Python by choosing an explicit and intentionally bounded form of mobility. A paglet moves as durable dataclass state plus a reference to already-installed behavior. The runtime supplies host management, process isolation, message passing, persistence, mesh discovery, and transport.

The result is not a universal distributed-computing abstraction. It is a practical tool for experiments and trusted environments where stateful work benefits from moving to the machine that has the data, services, devices, or local context. In that narrower domain, Paglets keeps the attractive

parts of the Aglets model while replacing implicit mobile-code assumptions with a Python-friendly operational contract.

References

- [1] Luca Ferrari. *The Aglets 2.0.2 User's Manual*, October 2004. Aglets project maintainer page announcing the manual, accessed 2026-06-23. URL: <https://aglets.sourceforge.net/maintainer.html>.
- [2] Foundation for Intelligent Physical Agents. FIPA abstract architecture specification. Technical Report SC00001L, Foundation for Intelligent Physical Agents, 2002. Archived from the original FIPA specification PDF, accessed 2026-06-23. URL: <https://web.archive.org/web/20241222024806/http://fipa.org/specs/fipa00001/SC00001L.pdf>.
- [3] Colin G. Harrison, David M. Chess, and Aaron Kershenbaum. Mobile agents: Are they a good idea? Technical Report RC 19887, IBM Research Division, 1995.
- [4] Carl Hewitt, Peter Bishop, and Richard Steiger. A universal modular actor formalism for artificial intelligence. In *Proceedings of the 3rd International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, pages 235–245, 1973. URL: <https://www.ijcai.org/Proceedings/73/Papers/027B.pdf>.
- [5] Christian Klukas. Paglets: A Python Aglets-inspired mobile object runtime, 2026. Software repository, accessed 2026-06-23. URL: <https://github.com/cklukas/paglets>.
- [6] Christian Klukas. Paglets documentation, 2026. Project documentation, accessed 2026-06-23. URL: <https://cklukas.github.io/paglets/>.
- [7] Danny B. Lange and Mitsuru Oshima. Programming mobile agents in Java with the Java Aglet API. IBM Research web draft mirror, 1997. Accessed 2026-06-23. URL: <https://www.cis.upenn.edu/~bcpierce/courses/629/papers/AgletsBook-index.html>.
- [8] Danny B. Lange, Mitsuru Oshima, Günter Karjoth, and Kazuya Kosaka. Aglets: Programming mobile agents in Java. In *Worldwide Computing and Its Applications*, volume 1274 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 253–266. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1997. doi:10.1007/3-540-63343-X_52.
- [9] Philipp Moritz, Robert Nishihara, Stephanie Wang, Alexey Tumanov, Richard Liaw, Eric Liang, Melih Elibol, Zongheng Yang, William Paul, Michael I. Jordan, and Ion Stoica. Ray: A distributed framework for emerging AI applications. In *13th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation*, pages 561–577, 2018. URL: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/osdi18/presentation/moritz>.
- [10] Matthew Rocklin. Dask: Parallel computation with blocked algorithms and task scheduling. In *Proceedings of the 14th Python in Science Conference*, pages 126–132, 2015. URL: <https://proceedings.scipy.org/articles/Majora-7b98e3ed-013>, doi:10.25080/Majora-7b98e3ed-013.
- [11] The Aglets Project. Aglets. SourceForge project website, 2004. Accessed 2026-06-23. URL: <https://aglets.sourceforge.net/>.